

The Great Controversy: Technology and the Loss of Face-to-Face Conversation

A response to Sherry Turkle's "The Flight From Conversation"

Revised Edition

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Abstract

This revised essay responds to Sherry Turkle's "The Flight From Conversation" (2012) by examining how overdependence on mobile and digital technologies erodes face-to-face relationships, cultural practices, and personal accountability. Drawing on data from the International Telecommunication Union (2024), World Health Organization (2022), American Psychological Association (2024), and Interpol (2024), the essay argues that while technology offers connection, it also increases risks of anxiety, depression, and cybercrime. The author calls for a return to direct conversation as an antidote to digital isolation.

Keywords: digital technology, face-to-face communication, Sherry Turkle, mental health, cybercrime, Philippines

We live in an era where mobile and digital technologies dominate daily life. As Sherry Turkle argues in "The Flight From Conversation" (2012), we are increasingly turning to our devices instead of to one another, and this shift carries social costs. Our devices, designed like modern Pandora's boxes, have changed how we relate to one another. Many of us now live like inmates behind invisible bars, constantly emitting, receiving, and transmitting signals. In our dependence on technology, we risk forgetting the customs and traditions that once held us together.

We use our phones to dissuade, entertain, flirt, inform, and persuade. We scroll through everything from erotic videos to sweet messages, from "patama lines" to simple hugot quotes. But pause for a moment. Look up from your screen. Do you even know who is sitting next to you? How long has it been since you spoke to them? After hours spent talking to a phone or staring at a computer, noticing the person beside you can feel unfamiliar. In that silence, we begin to see how far technology has pulled us apart.

We have become so attached to our gadgets that we forget the company right in front of us. The constant exposure to screens separates us from the

present moment. We post our grievances online without a second thought, believing that likes and shares can bridge the gaps between people.

Consider this: you may write 500 to 1,000 words a day and earn 1,000 likes and 50,000 reactions from 3,000 followers. That can feel like fame. But if those posts contain malicious information, offensive language, or harmful stories, what kind of reputation are you building? To those you have maligned or offended, you are not famous. You are simply careless.

Long before smartphones, people built strong relationships across vast distances. Arab and Chinese merchants traded with native Filipinos through barter. Kings sealed fellowship with blood compacts. Conflict has always existed — once with stones, spears, and bows; later with rifles, tanks, and rockets. Today, we fight a different war: against digital addiction, harmful radiation, and the erosion of real human connection.

Studies suggest that a large majority of people worldwide are heavily exposed to phones, computers, and other digital tools, with ~67% of the global

population using mobile services (International Telecommunication Union [ITU], 2024). Many have become victims of cyberbullying, identity theft, libel, extortion, and blackmail (Interpol, 2024). Others report eye strain, anxiety, and depression with heavy digital use (World Health Organization [WHO], 2022; American Psychological Association [APA], 2024). These costs show how deeply technology can affect us.

Imagine getting a call from a friend asking to meet at Hotel Jen Manila. You answer, then find yourself talking to yourself afterward, as if on a monologue. Or picture yourself smiling alone at a sweet message. We have become like puppets, moved by the strings of our devices, while convincing ourselves that we are “connected.”

On Facebook or Twitter, we forget distance, age, and time. Because we forget so much, we also forget what matters most: our friends, our family, our surroundings, and our relationship with God. We trade conversation for scrolling, and in doing so, we risk being forgotten ourselves.

So before it is too late, start a conversation. Nothing can replace talking face to face. Begin today.

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